

Response to Brian Kemple

A reaction to Kemple's "Signs of Unmeaning"

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I have a lot of respect for the contributions made by John Deely to semiotics, as well as to its history. In fact, I took the initiative to organize a tribute to him at the IASS conference in Kaunas, shortly after his untimely death. I also have some reasons to think that John, in the end, had a certain respect for my view, since he invited me to contribute to the *Semiotica* issue dedicated with his seminal book, *Four Ages of Understanding*, for which I wrote a paper which stated the same position as the one I put forward in my lecture, and John never contradicted what I said in that paper.

John was very different as a writer promulgating grand theories, and as someone you could encounter as a person at our conferences, not, of course, when he lectured or criticized other lecturers, but when you met him in-between those occasions. In those latter occasions, he was much more open-minded.

Although I have derived a lot of inspiration from Peirce, I think present-day Peircean orthodoxy is as a kind of strait-jacked applied to thinking, and Deelyism constitutes an even more constrained view on semiosis. I believe it is being truer to the spirit of Peirce's (and Deely's) work not to halt the process of inquiry, even when this includes the return to evaluate the contributions of earlier phases of the research tradition, as John did in the case of the Scholastics, but also including later phases of this tradition, such as that of the Enlightenment. Although I do not believe in God, I can still appreciate the work of the Scholastics. In a similar vein, as semioticians we should take into account the contributions of Enlightenment thinkers, although there is part of what they say that could retrospectively be considered nominalist. For my part, I have found that even declared near contemporary nominalists like Nelson Goodman have made interesting observations, although their observations must be translated back to vernacular thinking, or what I, in Husserl's terms, calls Lifeworld knowledge.

I live in a country in which philosophy was, in my youth, and still is, totally dominated by analytical philosophy. All my life, I have had to fight against nominalism, not for ideological reasons, but because I think it render any serious scientific inquiry impossible. Nevertheless, I think it is seriously misleading to project our present idea of nominalism back into history, and in this specific

case to the thinkers of the Enlightenment. I certainly agree that they were wrong, even naïve, to defend ideas which, in retrospect, could be labelled nominalist. But that should not impede us from taking into account other ideas which they were the first to formulate, and which have not been further elaborated afterwards in the research tradition of semiotics.

As for Kemple's first objection, the quotation which he offers only serves to confirm my interpretation. I have precisely quoted this passage in many of my papers. Contrary to what Kemple says, it is clear from this quotation that Peirce here "disavows the use of the term sign". And there are several other passages where he does the same thing. I am not saying that he afterwards continued in this sense, but only that he had (from my point of view) singular lucid moments, which also happen to concord with his own notion of the ethics of terminology. Let me be clear: for me, Peirce is an important thinker in the semiotic research tradition, but he is not the final authority.

I have basically already answered the second objection above, but let me just clarify that the research tradition to which I am referring is concerned with meaning, and that one important point is to separate the sign from a more general notion of meaning. Phenomenology has a lot to offer on that account. But, although one of Husserl's earliest writings was entitled "Semiotik", Husserl's definition of the sign, as opposed to other meanings, is insufficient, as I have showed in my papers.

As for the third objection, it is true that Peirce took a dim view of Husserl, and vice-versa, but that was, as least in part, because they were not very familiar with the work of the other. This is not strange, since, both in the case of Husserl and Peirce, most of their writings have only been accessible posthumously. And when you consider these writings, there are many parallels between their conceptions, as I have shown in many of my papers. One of the curious things I never understood about John was his predilection for Heidegger. I won't repeat the obvious fact: that Heidegger was not only a confirmed Nazi, but that his whole vision of philosophy predisposed him to take that stand. The important point, at present, is that, unlike Husserl, he did not promote the advance of inquiry, and Peirce would no doubt have recognized that.

So, I will continue to think that what is worthwhile in the semiotic thought tradition is the process of inquiry, as both Peirce and Husserl said, using different words, which means that none of them constitute the ultimate authority. The process must go on. And in that process, we cannot neglect anything that has been thought on semiotic matters before our time.